

SPATIAL

D4.1 Sociotechnical Analysis Framework

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Abstract	This document forms the basis for the sociotechnical embedded field analysis in the SPATIAL project. It provides a framework for determining the key processes and people to enable holistic technology development. The document presents a theoretical foundation based on Human Computer Interaction, Science and Technology Studies, and Practice Theory to enable an embedded field analysis focused on the social, legal, and technical limitations and gender and diversity considerations in AI development. The research design and analysis procedures provide insights into the practicalities of the multi-sited ethnographic analysis of AI tool development.
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D4.1: Sociotechnical Analysis Framework

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Dissemination Level		
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CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to SPATIAL project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The SPATIAL project includes an embedded field analysis to evaluate the sociotechnical circumstances of the development of SPATIAL tools. We will study how SPATIAL partners approach this process and related challenges, how they communicate as a partner and as a consortium, and what best practices they engage in. The setting of the SPATIAL project provides a valuable opportunity to study the development of trustworthy AI for cybersecurity, a new field of study and development with many unknowns.

This report outlines the foundations and design of the upcoming embedded field analysis of AI development processes in the SPATIAL project. This framework will facilitate the embedded engagement with project partners and help to determine key processes and people needed to produce a holistic picture of the technology development within this project.

The sociotechnical analysis framework is inspired by theoretical insights from Human Computer Interaction, Science and Technology Studies, and Practice Theory. Together, these fields of research will provide the means to evaluate the SPATIAL tool development, while considering more than technical development processes. Human Computer Interaction informs an emphasis on the historical and societal context of AI development, and guides a focus on interactions, joint performances, communication between humans and computers, and the values and ethics of technologies. Science and Technology Studies helps us to uncover the SPATIAL project as a case study and to situate AI development for cybersecurity in particular contexts, as well as to understand the interplay between social and technical elements. Practice Theory provides the tools to analyse AI development practices as meaningful assemblages of material and social dimensions.

The embedded field analysis is inspired by ethnographic research which has the goal of studying what (groups of) people do and say and allows us to observe AI development in situ. We will engage in a multi-sited ethnographic analysis following the development of SPATIAL tools by different project partners. In preparation of the fieldwork, we present an inventory of the SPATIAL practices and workflows. The fieldwork will include on-site (at partner companies) as well as digital fieldwork. Data collection includes (digital and in-person) interviews, observations of (digital and in-person) meetings, work activities and work environments, and the analysis of researcher fieldnotes, memos, digital documents, and digital communication.

The qualitative data will be analysed following the principles of thematic analysis, a method to identify, analyse, and report themes within data. We will use an iterative two-stage analysis procedure based on qualitative content analysis, identifying meaningful themes, while focusing on social, legal and technical limitations and gender and diversity considerations.

The embedded field analysis of SPATIAL tool development practices allows us to fully consider the challenges faced by project partners, and the ways in which these challenges are effectively overcome. The research will provide useful insights for a broader community of AI developers across domains, disciplines, and levels of expertise.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial intelligence
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
HCI	Human-Computer Interaction
PT	Practice Theory
SCOT	Social Construction of Technology
SSK	Sociology of Scientific Knowledge
STS	Science and Technology Studies
WP	Work package

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1 INTRODUCTION

The European Commission (EC) has identified artificial intelligence (AI) as a top priority for research and development, especially as AI-based tools are increasingly implemented in a range of societal contexts. One of the relatively new contexts in which AI is adopted is cybersecurity, where AI can offer improved security analytics and automated security measures, further reducing human involvement in securing digital infrastructures. This is an attractive prospect, as cybersecurity has also become a core competence and discipline for the European Union (EU) due to continuous technological innovation and digitalisation of (European) services and business. In commercial settings, AI for cybersecurity has gained interest as well, the market size accounted for US \$14.9 billion in 2021 [1]. However, issues with AI, both in this context and in general, remain on the topic of transparency, privacy, explainability, and several other aspects [2]. For this reason, unchecked development, and implementation of AI solutions for cybersecurity could potentially lead to increased vulnerability of digital infrastructures that the European Union (EU) and its citizens rely on.

In the endeavour to develop improved AI, the EC particularly supports efforts to develop trustworthy AI. The SPATIAL project aims to develop trustworthy AI for cybersecurity applications, by developing tangible measures to connect and embed ethics, robustness, and lawfulness into trustworthy AI, with a particular focus on privacy, accountability, and resilience as key characteristics of trustworthiness. However, in this process, the developers will encounter and need to weigh different experiences and demands of designers and users, technological potentials and limitations, and ethical, accountability, and privacy-preserving considerations. How developers approach and resolve such challenges during the development process of SPATIAL tools, should provide valuable insights into trustworthy AI development and relevant best practices. Therefore, the SPATIAL project includes an embedded field analysis to evaluate the sociotechnical circumstances of the development of SPATIAL tools. We will study how SPATIAL partners approach this process and related challenges in the project's use cases (see Appendix 1), how they communicate as a partner and as a consortium, and what best practices they develop while doing the work as part of the SPATIAL project.

1.1 SCOPE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE REPORT

This report presents the foundations and design of the upcoming embedded field analysis of development processes that are part of the SPATIAL project. The study is designed to enable embedded engagement with partners developing SPATIAL tools and technology for both industry and academic research settings. This setting allows us to study practices of AI development in situ. While regulations are in place to protect users, data subjects, and society, this happens after the fact and/or is enforced from a metalevel. By studying how AI developers perceive and mitigate concepts like bias, we aim to grasp relevant considerations to support understandings of the societal implications of AI and to share lessons learned with a larger community of AI-for-cybersecurity developers.

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The SPATIAL project provides a valuable opportunity to study the development of trustworthy AI for cybersecurity, a new field of study and development with many unknowns. The results will generate useful insights to AI developers across domains, disciplines, and levels of expertise. The primary goal of this report is to present a framework for sociotechnical analysis of SPATIAL tool development. This framework will facilitate the embedded engagement with project partners and will help to determine key processes and people needed to produce a holistic picture of the AI development within this project.

This report outlines the study's theoretical and methodological foundations, including the implications for the study's design. The design is inspired by theoretical insights from Human Computer Interaction, Science and Technology Studies, and Practice Theory. Together, these disciplines will provide the means to evaluate SPATIAL tool development, while taking into account more than technical development processes. These theoretical perspectives allow us to fully consider the effect of social, legal, and technical limitations, the gender and diversity considerations, and the ways in which any of these challenges can be effectively overcome.

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE REPORT

The next section presents the theoretical foundations for the embedded field analysis of SPATIAL tool development. The section begins by covering the fields of research of Human Computer Interaction and Science and Technology Studies, which is then followed by an exploration of Practice Theory. Section 3 is dedicated to ethnographic research, which guides the methodological approach to the sociotechnical analysis. The fourth section presents an inventory of SPATIAL practices and workflows and outlines the study design. The fifth section details the thematic analysis procedures. The final section provides an overview of the contents of this deliverable, opportunities, and limitations to keep in mind, and unfolds the next steps that follow the sociotechnical analysis.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

To provide a suitable framework for the sociotechnical analysis of SPATIAL tool development we need to explore and understand the different contexts in which development is happening and where SPATIAL tools might be deployed. These contexts go beyond the technical aspects as they are heavily intertwined with social aspects, such as organizational and institutional factors, economics, societal challenges, politics, and many more. For this reason, we borrow from the fields of research known as Human Computer Interaction (HCI) and Science and Technology Studies (STS). HCI focuses on the design of computer technology and the interactions between humans and computers. The latter forms a key focus for the embedded fieldwork wherein we will focus on how developers and computers interact in general, and in interactions between humans and algorithms designed for data processing and decision-making in particular. STS provides an understanding of how science and technology are embedded in social contexts, and how they reproduce and re-enact one another. This is combined with Practice Theory (PT), which is closely related to STS, but more concretely focuses on the way the social and the material are intertwined in the form of practices. As such, it can be considered that STS provides the ontological underpinnings of the embedded field analysis and PT provides a concrete focus for the empirical study. An overview of the theoretical foundations and key concepts for the sociotechnical analysis framework are visualised in Figure 1, below.

FIGURE 1: THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE EMBEDDED FIELD ANALYSIS

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2.1 HUMAN COMPUTER INTERACTION (HCI)

HCI is the first research approach that informs the SPATIAL embedded field analysis. HCI is “concerned with the design, evaluation and implementation of interactive computing systems for human use and with the study of major phenomena surrounding them” [3, p. 5]. In other words, the research scope of HCI includes technology design, evaluation, and implementation as well as the interaction between technologies and people, and how these are situated in social and societal contexts. The field of HCI emerged in the early 1980s when personal computing was introduced, and computers were no longer only used by information technology experts. The challenge of usability required additional skills and broadened the scope of computer science to human factors. This led to the inclusion of cognitive science in computer and software engineering and design, thus forming the basis for the field of HCI [4]. As of today, HCI forms a multidisciplinary research field which, amongst others, builds on computer science, sociology, anthropology, ergonomics, psychology, and industrial design [5].

The SPATIAL fieldwork approaches AI development from a sociological and anthropological perspective. We will analyse interactions between technology, work, and organization in HCI themes *joint performance of tasks by humans and machines, communication between humans and machines, and algorithms and programming* [3]. Hewett et al. describe humans as interacting social beings and emphasise how human and technical systems mutually adapt to each other and should be seen as sociotechnical systems [3]. Whereas HCI is often perceived as a technology-oriented field [6], the concept of sociotechnical systems provides tools for a broader focus [3]. This informs more recent HCI research focused on practices whereby technology is seen as one of many aspects of social situations [6].

HCI research is concerned with the values and ethics of digital technologies. Issues like misinformation, online harassment, exclusionary tools, and biased algorithms provide designers with challenges of great societal relevance [7]. Within HCI, conducting ethical design and avoiding biased practices have been important topics of investigation in the past decades. This is a complicated task because bias and unfairness take place in “*complex networks of designers, technological systems, users, and indirect stakeholders that make up our sociotechnical world*” [7, p. 11]. The complexity of sociotechnical networks increases because people and systems are thoroughly entangled. Moreover technologies and users often act and react in unpredictable ways, and technologies can have (societal) impact beyond users and direct stakeholders [7].

The field of HCI informs the sociotechnical analysis of SPATIAL tools in various ways. First, we take into account the historical and societal context of human computer interaction within the development of SPATIAL tools. Moreover, we are inspired by and build on insights from HCI research about joint performance of tasks by humans and machines, communication between humans and machines, and algorithms and programming. Finally, the focus of HCI research on values and ethics of technologies informs the goal of evaluating the social, legal, and technical limitations and gender and diversity considerations in AI development.

2.2 SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY STUDIES (STS)

The second theoretical underpinning of the sociotechnical analysis is STS. This field of research originated when scholars began to study the production of knowledge through scientific practice. The earliest work in this area provided an alternative perspective the mainstream view on science and scientific fact [8], [9]. The mainstream view, still commonly held by experts and non-experts, assumes that “scientific knowledge is objective, value-free, and discovered by specialists” and that technology is “a rather autonomous force in society” where its workings are “an intrinsic property of the technical machines and processes” [8, p. 21]. This view suggests that knowledge and technology are unambiguous and neutral phenomena that can be used to solve problems in an optimal way. This view can be problematic, already in scientific practice, but also because it tends to be extended to societal challenges, which are inherently complex and cannot be responded to with one solution [10].

Instead, STS scholarship builds on a constructivist view on science and scientific knowledge (sociology of scientific knowledge, SSK) [8], [11], and on technology (social construction of technology, SCOT) [8]. SSK scholars view scientific knowledge not as a given or something to be found (out), but instead as something that is construed by scientists through social processes. Experimental outcomes allow for different interpretations, or “interpretative flexibility” [8, p. 24], and the explanation that is accepted after discussions and negotiations is then accepted as scientific fact. Because of this, facts and knowledge are never neutral.

Technology and innovation are held in similar regard by STS scholars. One of the main aims for STS scholars is “*opening up the black box’ to demystify science and technology, that is, to analyse the process of production as well as the product*” [12, p. 198].

Those that perceive technology as being constructed argue that technologies do not hold a singular meaning and one clear path for future development. Current practices related to a particular technology tend to direct future use and developments, but this is not a deterministic relationship. Instead the social interactions, the meaning making practices, of social actors are more strongly involved in technological development [8]. Different social groups may end up with diverging social understandings of any particular technology, and multiple interpretations of technology can exist alongside one another, each as ‘real’ as the other. Which of the frames becomes accepted by social groups, is much more an issue of social processes than it is to any features of the technology itself. Thus, to understand how science and technology are constructed, it becomes important to know who is involved in the process and how.

For example, in relation to SPATIAL, AI technologies can be constructed differently by partners who follow different decision-making procedures and rules, adapt algorithms for a particular purpose, and teams including developers with different backgrounds. These factors in combination with the social understanding of AI by the developers, can (re)produce discrepancies, inequalities, or biases. Variations in the way that AI tools are constructed are likely to exist within the SPATIAL consortium, but they might have practical implications. It could affect how partners approach their development process and how different

conceptualisations of key characteristics (e.g., accountability, transparency, and explainability) materialise in project outcomes.

When considering how technologies might be constructed differently by different individuals or social groups, the focus tends to be on the role of people first and technology second. We aim to take a view that does not presume a leading role for either humans or technologies. In STS domains, this is in line with approaches that fall under material semiotics. Material semiotics consists of different approaches that share the aim to “*explore how the heterogeneous elements of the social-and-material overlap, influence one another, and generally fit themselves together [emphasis in the original], or not*” [13, p. 3]. The social and material are equally important here, because how phenomena come into being cannot be understood without analysing the role that the social and the material play [14]. However, in material semiotics, neither the social nor the material take precedence. Instead, *how they relate (in meaningful ways) and how these relations come into being* are of interest. In tracing and studying such relations, it becomes relevant to include not just the people involved, but also to consider how tools and spaces might affect the outcomes, as well as how they change over time.

Consequently, research that is grounded in material semiotics, but also STS more broadly, is highly contextual and findings should always be (re)viewed as being connected to the situation from which they emerge [13]. Case studies are therefore the main approach for STS [11], [13]. For the sociotechnical analysis framework, we consider the SPATIAL project as a case to uncover. More specifically, within this project, there are four partners who provide a use case for which SPATIAL tools will be developed (see Appendix 1). These four cases provide us with the opportunity to situate and contextualise AI development for cybersecurity in particular contexts, as well as to understand the interplay between the social and the material. This will enable us to identify and distil helpful practices that can be shared with the broader AI development community.

2.3 PRACTICE THEORY (PT)

The final theory informing the sociotechnical analysis is closely related to Science and Technology Studies and has become influential in HCI research in the past decades. This approach is PT. PT aims to understand social life through practices [15]. Similar to STS, key to practices is that they not only exist of social actions, but also of material elements. In light of material semiotics, covered above, Law argues that practices are “*simultaneously semiotic (because they are relational, and/or they carry meanings) and material (because they are about the physical stuff caught up and shaped in those relations)*” [13, p. 1].

In PT, this is conceptualised as sociomateriality. Sociomateriality indicates that the social and the technical are inseparable within practices and because practices exist of matter and culture [16]. As Orlikowski states, “*the social and the material are constitutively entangled in everyday life... humans are constituted through relations of materiality – bodies, clothes, food, devices, tools, which, in turn, are produced through human practices*” [17, p. 1437]. Sociomateriality entails the interdependence of social and material dimensions of practices.

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This is also visible in Schatzki's definition of practices as "*embodied, materially mediated arrays of human activity centrally organised around shared practical understanding*" [18, p. 11]. 'Materially mediated' refers to how practices are interwoven with material and embodied elements, relating sociomateriality to the fact that objects form constitutive components of practices. Reckwitz presents a practice as a "*routinised type of behaviour which consists of several elements, interconnected to one another: forms of bodily activities, forms of mental activities, 'things' and their use, a background knowledge in the form of understanding, know-how, states of emotion and motivational knowledge*" [19, p. 248].

These definitions are reconceptualised by Shove et al. [20] who argue that practices come into being when three interconnected dimensions interact, namely competencies, meanings, and materials. *Materials* refers to objects or 'things' paramount to practices, such as tools, objects, hardware, infrastructures and bodies. According to Schatzki [15], most actions cannot take place without objects. In the sociotechnical analysis proposed, the material dimension of AI design include tangible, digital, human, and non-human elements, such as computer screens, laptops, digital interfaces, (home) office environments, computer code, and bodies.

To successfully engage in practices, an "*understanding and practical knowledgeability*" is required [20, p. 23]. This dimension is presented as *competence* and includes know-how, background information, and practical skills along with rules, principles, and explicit instructions. For AI design practices, this can entail practical knowledge about particular functionalities of coding languages, knowledge about which data provide the input for an algorithm, an understanding of machine learning requirements, or know-how about how to deploy federated learning. A crucial focus of the sociotechnical analysis is awareness of ethical implications and the consequences of particular AI design choices. Here it becomes visible how AI development practices not only revolve around technical expertise but also around tacit knowledge of social norms and societal implications.

The material and the competence dimensions would not be carried out without a particular purpose. *Meaning* can be understood as the social and symbolic significance of practices which can overlap as well as divert across practices [20]. Within the SPATIAL project, the meaning of AI development practices differs across use cases, whereas some use cases have a cyber security related goal, others are focused on privacy-preserving data analysis. However, a shared purposes of achieving trustworthy, transparent and explainable AI fuels the collaborative efforts of SPATIAL practices.

Practices are often not limited to one location; they can be seen as co-located practice bundles emerging in different contexts [20]. Practices shape each other and change over time. Change to practices is brought by internal factors like experimentation and improvisation of practitioners and by external factors such as adjacent practices, institutional arrangements, economic situations, and technological innovations [21]. In the sociotechnical analysis we will focus on co-located practices in SPATIAL work and how these are geared towards more transparent AI development practices.

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More specifically, we will use PT to guide our empirical research. We perceive AI development as an assemblage of sociomaterial practices. Studying practices means shifting social analysis from individuals to practices, to doings taking place in specific situational settings, in order to go “back to the social roots of meaningful experience” [22, p. 156]. Instead of focusing on opinions or attitudes, the focus lies on what people do and how their practices are inherently social as well as material. Throughout processes of observing AI development practices, constructing interview guides, talking to AI developers, analysing meeting transcripts, generating memos, and reporting the most prevalent findings, we will be most attentive to what people do rather than what they think, believe, or know.

When AI developers describe their work practices, they automatically touch upon the materials included as well as the social considerations behind their everyday actions. It is not that individual beliefs, perceptions, and opinions are not interesting; rather it tells much more when it is clear how these are embedded in sociomaterial activities, social contexts, and patterns of reproduced practices. The focus on sociomaterial practices enables an analysis of AI development as a meaningful assemblage of material and social dimensions.

2.4 KEY TAKEAWAYS

- HCI informs the sociotechnical embedded field analysis as it informs an emphasis on historical and societal contexts of human computer interaction, guides a focus on *joint performance of tasks by humans and machines*, *communication between humans and machines*, and *algorithms and programming*, and helps to analyse values and ethics of technologies in evaluating the social, legal, and technical limitations and gender and diversity considerations in AI development for cybersecurity.
- STS helps us to uncover the SPATIAL project as a case study and understand the elements as sociomaterial assemblages. The four use cases in the SPATIAL project provide us with the opportunity to situate AI development for cybersecurity in particular contexts, as well as to understand the interplay between the social and the material. This will enable us to identify and distil helpful practices that can be shared with the broader AI development community.
- PT provides the tools to analyse AI development practices. We will study AI development as a meaningful assemblage of material and social dimensions and will investigate how AI developers engage in SPATIAL framework development practices.

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3 ETHNOGRAPHIC FIELDWORK

The previous section showed that AI development practices can be meaningfully studied as an assemblage of material and social dimensions. There are methodological implications for studying practices, as practices must “*inevitably happen in concrete moments and specific situational settings*” [22, pp. 156–157]. Therefore, to study AI development practices, we must enter the contexts where such practices occur or are performed. This way, we can create deeper understanding of these sociomaterial assemblages, which actors are involved, and how they are woven together. For this reason, we will conduct a study with an ethnographic approach, which will enable us to observe AI development practices at different times and in different spaces.

3.1 ETHNOGRAPHY

Ethnography has a rich history in the field of anthropology, where researchers would study cultural groups and understand their way of life [23]–[25]. To do this, they “*have entered the spaces of their participants to gain a deeper understanding of how people experience, perceive, create, and navigate the social world*” [24, p. 307]. Ethnography has become a valuable methodology for social science as well, though its principles and related practices have adapted accordingly. Ethnography as a methodology in social science research is marked by shorter times spent with the social group of interest [23], and it is more flexible in the way that supplementary data collection is integrated. What remains unchanged, however, is that this ethnographic research “*emphasizes the importance of studying at first hand [emphasis in original] what people do and say in particular contexts*” [23, p. 4]. Key to this methodology is to observe the social group of interest and to make a record of what they do, what they say, and how they go about life. Therefore, observation remains the key method for data collection in ethnographic research.

There are different approaches to observing an ethnographer may take. According to Gold's typology, there are four distinct roles for an ethnographer: 1) the complete participant; 2) the participant-as-observer; 3) the observer-as-participant; and 4) the complete observer [26]. The complete participant fully immerses themselves with the social group of interest, participates in their practices, and does not make their role as researcher known to those they observe. The participant-as-observer shares characteristics with the total participant, however, generally the researcher's identity and role are known to the group they are observing. The third role, the observer-as-participant, is more common when the research involves one-time visits or relatively short encounters with research participants, which leaves less time to participate than the previous two roles. The last role identified by Gold, the total observer, is the most distanced of the four roles. In this role, the ethnographer does not interact with the research participants. Consequently, the participants might not be aware of the ethnographer's aims, nor that they or their practices are being studied. This last role tends to be combined with one of the other roles, as there will be moments where participants are not aware that particular practices are of interest to the ethnographer.

Which of these roles is suitable depends on the type of research question the ethnographer aims to answer, the type of role that is available, and ethical considerations of what is possible and what is appropriate for obtaining the necessary data. Moreover, regardless of which role the researcher takes on, the researcher always has an active role in the creation of research data and constructing the results. Researchers need to find the right balance between going native and accept the informant's views as their own, and ethnocentrism characterised by a lack of meaningful interaction with informants (sometimes even rejecting the informants perspective) [26, p. 222].

Following Latour and Woolgar [11], an STS-informed ethnographic study requires reflexivity on how research data is produced and results are constructed. The researcher, coming from a particular background, always influences knowledge production. However, as suggested previously, the nature of the influence may differ depending on the role the researcher takes. Moreover, reflexivity is also required on how the research might affect research participants. We need to be aware of and act upon the fact that our study does not exist externally from the development work with regards to the SPATIAL tools. In the words of Law and Urry, *"the social sciences have always been embedded in, produced by, and productive of the social"* [27, p. 392]. Therefore, a reflexive approach on our methods for study and how they might affect the contexts we study is imperative.

Ethnographers hold informal interviews with participants and make fieldnotes to supplement observational data [24]. Other relevant data may be extracted from documents, images, audio, or video recordings of salient moments, and many more. Taken together, the ethnographer will be able to put their observations and fieldnotes (e.g., interpretations, comments) into context. In the SPATIAL embedded sociotechnical analysis, we expect to take on the role of an observer-as-participant (while realising that these roles are flexible). We and our research goals are known to the AI developers within SPATIAL. The fieldwork will be based on interviews and the observation of work activities and meetings during one, or two-time visits. Throughout the fieldwork we aim to reflect on our own influence as researchers. Moreover, we will engage in an ongoing digital analysis of meetings and digital interactions. The next section provides more insights into multi-sited and digital ethnography.

3.2 MULTI-SITED AND DIGITAL ETHNOGRAPHY

Ethnography used to take place at one site, which tends to be organised around geographic sites or areas [24], [25]. This provides the ethnographer with the opportunity to investigate in high detail how participants live their day-to-day (work) lives. However, lives are lived beyond the limits of one particular site and in order to understand how practices are taken up and performed at different sites, ethnographers need to follow their participants to these places.

Multi-sited ethnography should include the digital space, or the online habitat [24]. With the emergence and integration of digital technologies in everyday life (e.g., for socialising, organising, working, shopping, and many more), we consider that the materiality of many practices has changed. Digital technologies cannot be discounted when wanting to understand

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contemporary life in all areas [24], though the ubiquity of these technologies seems to have made them less visible as factors of consequence [28]. In the context of the SPATIAL project, digital technologies become especially salient, due to the dependence on digital technologies to design, develop, and implement AI tools, but also due to the way these technologies facilitate communication and working-from-home practices. Thus, we agree with Hallett and Barber [24], that contemporary ethnography should include digital sites. Important here is that, in line with the perspective of HCI, STS and PT, the focus remains on the relations between online and offline, between social and material, because only through these relations we are able to provide a thorough description of particular phenomena, in this case, AI development.

There are no specific guidelines or requirements for designing a practice-based ethnography [28], nor digital ethnography. This can be a risk, as Hallett and Barber [22] warn, because participants may not be aware of the role those digital technologies play or their significance. As such, ethnographers should design their study in a way that highlights relevant practices, and ethnographic interviews that elicit appropriate responses. Below, we outline several considerations that will provide more practical insights for the sociotechnical analysis framework.

According to Marcus [25], there are different ways to design multi-sited ethnographic research, that will allow the ethnographer to strategically move between different sites. Two of Marcus' suggestions are of interest for our fieldwork, one is to "follow the people," and the other is to "follow the thing" [25, pp. 106–107]. To follow the people means to join participants at the different sites they are active in and observe them. This approach would steer us in joining our partners in the various physical and digital environments where they perform the work related to SPATIAL tool development. The second option, to follow the thing, would entail the ethnographer entering the different sites where a product is designed, developed, produced, and, if applicable, sold [19]. Taking this approach, will steer our focus towards the various stages of SPATIAL tool development and to elicit the different practices that are relevant to each stage. In this approach, it also becomes possible to see how practices change or evolve over time, which connects well to the perspective of STS-focused research.

These two approaches need not exclude one another, and, in fact, combining them may provide valuable insights that will not be possible if applied independently. Following the people involved, sometimes in moments that do not involve dedicated AI development practices, could help us uncover relevant practices that are indirectly involved, but of influence. And following the thing might help us uncover how SPATIAL tools are understood by relevant actors outside of the SPATIAL project.

Previous research has provided concrete options for designing ethnographic research that incorporates digital tools which can serve as supplemental tools for the fieldwork. One of such tools incorporates tours of relevant sites. This tool considers buildings as "*a material and social space that is an active methodological resource*" [29, p. 683]. Just as digital technologies and their influence may be taken for granted, so might be the influence of physical spaces. This tool is designed for participants to take the researcher along on a tour through a space or building,

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their workplace, for example. During such a tour, participants provide commentary on how they use the space, the separate areas, and the objects within these areas. This provides insight into different practices: related to work, to socialisation, to organisation, and other practices that might occur in this context. By taking such tours, participants will be supported in recounting and explaining their experiences by moving through the physical space and being present in the moment. This can provide surprising insights, more so than interviews, that are comparatively static and based in a single location, removed from the actual practice site [29]. This particular tool may be useful when conducting site visits of SPATIAL partners (if those are possible).

The second tool that can prove useful is the media go-along. Originally, this method was devised for ethnographers to accompany participants in daily and/or social activities whereby the participant talks the researcher through their practices. The go-along method is suitable for studying experiences, decision-making, and thought-processes in real-time [30]. This method requires the researcher to take an “*active stance towards capturing their informants’ actions and interpretation*” [31, p. 463]. The go-along method is also deployed for studying media use, as the media go along, whereby the researcher observes how a participant uses media devices and digital media. Participants are interviewed while they use or access media whereby they have direct access to (social) media, their accounts and interactions [32]. The same approaches can be valuable in SPATIAL fieldwork because interviewing participants (digitally or in-person) while they have direct access to their work devices and conversations might enable them to better reflect on their actual practices than when they are separated from their work.

Another valuable digital ethnography tool is the scroll-back method. This method was originally designed to study social media disclosure practices as it asks research participants to scroll through their social media accounts, and by accessing their historical digital traces, they use their timelines as memory objects [32]. In SPATIAL fieldwork, a similar approach can be helpful to trace back past interactions and decision-making processes. Moreover, it can be a way to work around sensitive conversations because the participants can disclose what they wish by scrolling through interactions and only sharing details that they deem relevant. It can also help to cross potential language barriers that we might come across, as participants might not discuss work in English, but instead converse in their native or local language.

3.3 KEY TAKEAWAYS

- To study the development of SPATIAL tools in the context of cybersecurity specifically and AI more broadly as sociomaterial practices, we will design our fieldwork based on ethnographic principles. This will allow us to gain a deeper understanding of the relationships between the social and the material, which actors are involved, and how they are woven in particular situations and contexts. More specifically, studying AI development requires an analysis of developer practices, perceptions, interactions, and (digital) communication. Ethnographic fieldwork allows for in-depth and comprehensive analyses of different types of data during longer time periods and therefore it is most suitable for the social sciences research in the SPATIAL project.

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- Social life occurs beyond individual sites, so contemporary ethnographic research should be multi-sited, meaning that it should be conducted beyond singular concrete sites. Our partners combine working in the office with working from home, and much of their work occurs in the digital sphere. Our study will benefit from following both the people working on the project and following the SPATIAL tools in the digital space. The fieldwork design needs to correspond with this way of working, by means of digital ethnographic tools.
- Ethnography, whether traditional or digital, relies on observations, interviews, fieldnotes or memos, and reviewing organisational documentation (where relevant). In addition to these, we will make use of tools that will enable us to elicit responses that highlight the role of digital technologies. These are tours of significant sites, go-along activities, and the scroll-back method.
- During the fieldwork, we will need to be reflexive on our role as social scientists and be aware of and act upon the fact that our study is in fact embedded in the development work with regards to the SPATIAL tools. What we observe during the fieldwork might be useful to construct as best practices and shared with the larger AI development community. In this way, we are part of the knowledge construction even without being part of the technical team.

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4 STUDY DESIGN AND PRACTICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The theoretical foundation of HCI, STS, and PT presented in the second section of this report, together with the insights into ethnographic fieldwork from the previous section form the basis for the sociotechnical analysis. What follows is an overview of how we inventoried SPATIAL practices, a mapping of the SPATIAL workflow, and the study design for the embedded analysis with an ethnographic approach.

4.1 INVENTORY OF SPATIAL PRACTICES

In preparation of the plans for the sociotechnical analysis, multiple meetings were held providing valuable input for the study design presented below. In April 2022 the Work Package (WP) 4 kick-off meeting was held, where we presented the plans for the analysis and had a valuable discussion of the work to be conducted within SPATIAL, and how to extract best practices and ways of working. This discussion highlighted that cybersecurity is the primary umbrella of work within SPATIAL and that the use cases offer different focus points within the cyber security domain. Moreover, the interesting connection between interface design and verbal interfaces was discussed as a potential interesting focus of the analysis.

In May 2022, we held exploratory meetings with the four use case leads, the partner involved with the framework used in some use cases, and the leader of WP3. In these meetings we began to build individual connections with the use case partners and got to know the people working for each partner better, as well as gained more information about each partner's way of working. During these conversations, we reiterated the purpose and plans for the sociotechnical analysis and provided the partners with the opportunity for asking clarifying questions. We prepared questions about the partner organization, their team, their way of working, and what (digital) tools they use. Other questions were aimed at clarification about the partner's role in the project, their aims for the use case, and how they envision to achieve their goals. These meeting provided us with basic information about how SPATIAL work is integrated in each partner's broader workflow, including detailed information of the individual partners, internal decision-making and communication processes, and the people involved. As such, these conversations inform the next sections wherein we map SPATIAL workflows and outline the research design.

4.2 MAPPING SPATIAL WORKFLOW

Given that sociotechnical analysis entails a study of AI for cybersecurity development practices, ways of working, and interactions, it is important to map how partners involved in the use cases work. This matters on two levels. The first is the project-level, in the SPATIAL project multiple means of communication and collaboration are used.

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- Project management: Emdesk (project management software) includes an overview of all the tasks and the progress for all tasks and related output, documents (such as reports and minutes), real-time budgets, and email lists.
- Day-to-day communication: Email forms the main communication channel for SPATIAL messages, in addition dedicated Microsoft Team environments are used for some dedicated tasks/work packages.
- Digital Meetings: Microsoft Teams, Zoom, and Google Meet.
- Collaboration: Microsoft Teams, Google Drive, and Overleaf for digital collaborations, Concept Board for brainstorming activities.

The second level concerns the company-level. The project partners that are participants in the embedded field analysis are based in different companies. Apart from the earlier mentioned tools that are used project-wide, the companies also mentioned additional software that they use in their team while developing SPATIAL tools:

- Day-to-day communication: Slack, Microsoft Teams, WhatsApp
- Task management and collaboration: Jira scrum board, Confluence collaboration tool, ticketing software
- Programming: Code repositories like GitLab or GitHub

Key here is how the individual companies organise work and how the SPATIAL activities are distributed over different people. The common denominator of the different companies is that they work in small teams whereby one or two employees are the contact persons and project leads. Their teams include early career professionals, PhD students, and/or postdoctoral researchers. The configuration of the teams changes regularly in some of the companies. Finally, in all companies, employees work mostly from home and partly from the office. This means that SPATIAL AI development happens in multiple locations, limiting the opportunity for and relevance of company visits. Therefore, the digital counterpart of the fieldwork is crucial.

4.3 STUDY DESIGN

The embedded field analysis is guided by a focus on the interaction between humans and technology (informed by HCI), the material semiotic aspects of these interactions (STS-inspired), and on AI development practices (following PT). In practice, this means that we will ask questions about and observe **how** SPATIAL partners do their work and keep a focus on how material elements play a role in the interactions between technologies and participants.

The fieldwork takes place from Fall 2022 to Spring 2023. During these months, we will collect and analyse (recordings of) the meetings and communication in Work Package 3 'System Architecture, Consistency and Accountability for AI, Validation and Testing'. Moreover, we will study the work done in that period by the individual partners involved in the development of SPATIAL tools. In preparation for the field analysis, we received ethical approval from the EUR Ethics Review Committee of our research design and our data management plan.

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In September 2022, we will contact the abovementioned partners to plan an initial round of interviews, to inventory digital content valuable for the analysis, and to plan location visits (if possible and relevant). We will also ask for their explicit consent to the research activities, to make sure that all parties involved are fully aware of our research aims and activities. The different research activities and focus are outlined below and a visual summary is provided in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2: OVERVIEW OF STUDY DESIGN

4.3.1 EMBEDDED FIELD ANALYSIS: ON-SITE FIELDWORK

The on-site fieldwork will include in person data collection via interviews, observations, and researcher fieldnotes. First, we will ask participants to provide us a tour of their workplace, to the extent that this is possible. This will already provide us with some insights into the workflow that is relevant for this partner. During these tours, we might ask clarifying questions and make fieldnotes. As previous chapters indicated, digital technologies and how they play a role at these sites are of particular interest.

Second, we will conduct semi-structured in-depth interviews. In-depth interviews allow for studying complex social experiences [29], [33], while semi-structured interviews follow an interview guide that leaves room for flexibility and input from the participants. This helps to build rapport with the participants, and allows them to answer interview questions in a more relaxed and organic manner [34]. In the interviews, we will ask participants to tell us more about the work they are doing for SPATIAL, how they collaborate with colleagues, and about the particular social, legal, and technical limitations that they encounter as well as considerations they make around gender and diversity, about if and how they avoid bias in their work, how

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they work towards transparency and trustworthiness (in general and in SPATIAL specific research). To study their digital communication practices and the topics that they discuss with colleagues, we plan to implement a scroll-back activity [32] (see previous section). For this, participants will be asked to scroll through SPATIAL related conversations on the communication platform they use most often and share what type of conversations they see and what issues and challenges they have encountered in the context of the SPATIAL project. We will make audio-recordings of the interviews, which will be later transcribed and analysed.

Second, the observations of SPATIAL-related work will be done during location visits, SPATIAL-related meetings, and work activities we will witness. We will ask the partners we visit to allow us to work in the same room as them to get a feel of the work environment and to, if the conditions allow, observe them when they are working on building SPATIAL tools.

Third, researcher fieldnotes and memos will be made during and after these observations and will form another set of research data. Fieldnotes and memos can also cover informal conversations and in order to create transparency about this, we will indicate this clearly to the participants before the start of the research.

4.3.2 EMBEDDED FIELD ANALYSIS: DIGITAL FIELDWORK

The digital counterpart of the embedded field analysis entails the analysis of online meetings, digital interviews, digital observations, and the analysis of digital documents and communication. First, digital fieldwork concerns observations and analysis of online meetings. We have already started observations of WP3 meetings (which all partners involved provided explicit consent for). We join the WP3 meetings and make notes during the meetings. We also receive recordings of the meetings which will be transcribed and analysed. Moreover, we hope to also engage in observations of digital meetings about SPATIAL tool development of the project partners involved in the fieldwork. Multiple partners have indicated that they are willing to do this. For these meetings, we do not expect to receive recordings, but we will join digitally and make notes during the meetings.

Second, digital interviews will cover the same methods and topics as the on-site interviews. The difference here is that these interviews take place via Microsoft Teams or Zoom, whereby we will ask participants to switch their camera on. Digital interviews can constrain the interviewer in establishing rapport and engaging in a comfortable conversation with the participants. Yet, on the other hand, participants of digital interviews are in their own environment which might make it easier to feel comfortable in the interview setting.

Third, to allow for digital observations of AI development we will ask partners to engage in one or more go-along interviews as described in the previous section [30], [32]. In these interviews, we will interview partners while they talk us through their work activities, if possible while sharing their screen via Zoom or Teams. This research method provides the opportunity to interview developers about their work practices while they have their work at hand and can

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easily show what they talk about and are more engaged with the topic at hand than they would be in an isolated setting.

Finally, digital documents and communication will be analysed. This concerns the analysis of digital documents exchanged via email and/or project management software Emdesk. Such documents concern the minutes of meetings, project reports, specifics about decisions that were made, and project-related communication via digital collaboration platforms. Digital communication like Slack or Teams conversations and internal emails and additional documentation that are not available via SPATIAL channels will be provided by the project partners (meaning that this will be limited to content that project partners are willing to share).

As indicated throughout this report, the embedded field analysis focuses on the social, legal, and technical limitations and gender and diversity considerations in AI development. In practice, this means that we will explore these topics in interviews and that they are a key focus of the (digital) observations. For studying diversity, it is important to consider that apart from the international orientation of the consortium (project partners are based in Finland, Estonia, Serbia, Ireland, the Netherlands, Germany, France, and Spain), the local teams are also diverse as they include professionals with a variety of nationalities (French, Russian, Vietnamese, Dutch, Chinese, and others).

We focus on communication and collaborations in the project and on how concepts like trustworthiness, accountability, transparency, and explainability (which are defined in project deliverable 1.1) materialise in everyday practices. All research practices will take into account the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and additional legal regulations. Moreover, to ensure internal validity of this study within the project, we will regularly return to the participating project partners and ask them to respond to particular quotes/findings.

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5 ANALYSIS AND POTENTIAL FIELDWORK OUTCOMES

The fieldwork will produce a large set of qualitative data from different sources, produced in various locations and at different times. This data set will provide insight into the meaningful experiences surrounding AI development, as from the perspective from our project partners. We intend to extract relevant knowledge about AI development practices from these experiences [35]. Our analysis will be informed by the principles of thematic analysis, as outlined below. The results from this process will form the basis for a scientific article, the intended output related to the fieldwork. Beyond this, the themes that we might uncover through our data will provide useful insights into best practices related to the development of secure, privacy-preserving, accountable AI for cybersecurity.

5.1 THEMATIC ANALYSIS

The data gathered in the fieldwork (documents, interview recordings, memos, and notes) form the basis of an in-depth analysis following the principles of thematic analysis. In the words of Braun and Clarke [36, p. 79]: “*Thematic analysis is a method for identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data.*” Thematic analysis allows the researcher to highlight commonalities in the data in an inductive manner. It is a flexible method that allows researchers to deal with a large volume of complex data, though this requires the researchers to report in detail about their analysis process and the choices they made to develop a consistent and coherent account of the results [35]. Thematic analysis is focused on the experiences, practices, opinions, interactions, and processes visible in the data, rather than applying a lens of existing theories to the data [36]. However, the analysis will be guided by the theoretical assumptions outlined in Section 2 and the key focus points of the WP4; social, legal, and technical limitations and gender and diversity considerations.

In thematic analysis, themes are found by allocating codes to the data and finding commonalities amongst the codes [35], [36]. For the analysis, we will use qualitative coding software *Atlas.ti* and follow a two-stage iterative coding procedure. The first coding phase revolves around open coding. After reading the transcripts and noting down initial ideas, we will allocate codes to text fragments in the data. A code is a word or short phrase that portrays the meaning or salience of a section of text. The code can be formulated verbatim by using the exact words from the data or via a descriptor. To avoid individual biases and to ensure similar approaches to the research process, a portion of the data set will be double-coded. This means that two researchers will code the same section and compare the open coding afterwards. This will help us to avoid inconsistencies or ambiguities in the coding and warrants reliability of the analysis.

In the second phase, the collection of open codes will be clustered into themes. A theme describes important aspects of the data in relation to the research question. Ideally, a theme presents itself in multiple data sources, but the frequency of a code does not necessarily determine the significance of the theme. Clustering the open codes into themes will be a

collaborative effort between the researchers to ensure agreement about and clarity of the themes. We will pay particular attention to nuances, contradictions, and contrasts existing in the data set. It will be crucial to review the themes before these are finalised [36]. A quality-check of the themes in relation to the entire data set will be done to assess their frequency and we will revisit and re-read the transcripts and add, adjust, or merge codes where needed. Such reflexivity is essential to thematic analysis, as its flexibility can detract from a consistent and systematic approach to the data set [35]. Based on this reflexive and iterative process, we will be able to finalise univocal definitions for each theme.

5.2 RESEARCH FINDINGS

The sociotechnical analysis framework is intended to set the parameters for an embedded engagement with partners, however, we would like to look towards what the outcomes of this research might offer us.

Since we take an inductive approach to our data analysis, we cannot provide any specific preconceptions about what results we might obtain from the sociotechnical analysis. However, as an indication, we can offer a preliminary reflection. We have already come across the variations in the language and vocabulary that different partners use. Through meeting participation, we have witnessed how partners identify variations in understanding of SPATIAL concepts (e.g., transparency, security, explainability) and have already seen how the partners aim to resolve this. We expect to observe similar processes during the data collection and believe they might be valuable to our partners, but also the AI community beyond the SPATIAL project.

The themes resulting from the two-stage analysis will be presented in a publicly available and peer reviewed scientific research article defining AI development practices. The article will also serve as reading material for the education module to be developed in Task 4.5.

The findings will also inform (part of) our future work in which we will determine the aspects that will have significant issues or impacts in relation to the social, legal, and ethical concerns inherent in producing explainable and transparent AI. Through our observations of AI development practices, we will be able to see potential tensions that our partners have to navigate. For example, partners might have to choose between compliance with privacy and data protection laws and the ability for this to occur based on algorithmically determined analyses of information. Observing how such tensions are approached by the different partners, and with what outcomes, will help us to extract and translate best practices and communicate those to the broader AI development community.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The work in Task 4.1 resulted in this framework for the sociotechnical analysis which outlines the theoretical and empirical foundation for the embedded field analysis as well as the practicalities of the research design and analysis procedures.

The fields of research of HCI, STS, and PT provide a theoretical foundation that provide the means to evaluate SPATIAL tool development, while taking into account more than technical development processes. HCI informs the sociotechnical embedded field analysis as it informs an emphasis on the historical and societal context of human computer interaction, guides a focus on interactions, joint performances, and communication between humans and computers in general, and AI and developers in specific, and helps to analyse values and ethics of technologies. STS helps us to uncover the SPATIAL project as a case study with the opportunity to situate and contextualise AI development for cybersecurity in particular contexts, as well as to understand the interplay between the social and the material. PT provides the tools to analyse SPATIAL tool development practices. We will study AI development as a meaningful assemblage of material and social dimensions and will investigate how AI developers engage in SPATIAL tool development practices.

The ethnographic fieldwork will focus on the social, legal and technical limitations and gender and diversity considerations. The research context is the development of SPATIAL tools by multiple project partners. The multi-sited empirical research will entail on-site (at partner companies) as well as digital fieldwork. Data collection is based on (digital and in-person) interviews, observations of (digital and in-person) meetings, work activities and work environments, and the analysis of researcher fieldnotes, memos, digital documents, and communication.

The qualitative research data will be analysed following the principles of thematic analysis and the themes resulting from the two-stage inductive analysis will be presented in a publicly available and peer reviewed scientific research article defining AI development practices with a focus on social, legal, and technical limitations and gender and diversity considerations.

6.1 CONSIDERATIONS AND LIMITATIONS

Throughout this report, we have indicated points of consideration and potential limitations to our research. First, the nature of our theoretical and methodological approach is inherently contextual. Moreover, each partner aims to develop their use case of interest, which have little overlap. This means that we might encounter a high variance in AI development practices and approaches per partner, which may affect how we might organise our findings. However, because all partners work towards SPATIAL goals of secure, privacy-accountable technologies, explainability, and transparency, we expect to be able to find commonalities and practices that are of broader interest to the AI community.

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Second, there may be limitations for implementing our study, or variations in what is possible to do with each use case partner. Different team sizes, working from home practices, and privacy considerations concerning partners' clients might affect how we implement the sociotechnical analysis framework. We will work with our partners to explore all opportunities and remain flexible in our approach; this framework provides an overarching plan that we can adjust so that it fits with each partner's context and use case. Should Covid infections rise again, we will likely reorient our embedded fieldwork to lean even more on digital methods.

Finally, throughout the fieldwork and analysis we will have to remain aware of our role as social scientists in the (re)production of AI development practices, even potentially harmful or detrimental ones. A reflexive stance and critical review of our work, as a team, but also with our project partners, will ensure that we will not overlook the effect that our presence might have as observers and participants in the SPATIAL project.

6.2 NEXT STEPS

The publication resulting from the embedded field analysis will be a key literature reference point for the education module and highlight the crucial social aspects for increasing explainability and transparency in AI development. Moreover, this publication will inform the intended processes and practices for the deployment and demonstrations in WP5. Now that the framework has been outlined, the next steps are geared towards ensuring that the results will be valuable within the SPATIAL project but also towards disseminating useful insights towards a broader community of AI developers across domains, disciplines, and levels of expertise.

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APPENDIX A: DESCRIPTION OF USE CASES

In this appendix, we provide a short summary of the four use cases that are part of the SPATIAL project. This information, as also included the project website (see <https://spatial-h2020.eu/validation/>), provides additional context for the structure, content, and point of departure for the sociotechnical analysis framework.

Use case 1: Privacy-preserving AI on the Edge and beyond

SPATIAL partner Telefónica leads this use case with the goal of designing and implementing a Communications Framework for AI Privacy applications. It focuses on the performance of privacy-preserving machine learning – AI methods (classical, as well as deep learning methods) when deployed on edge computing nodes expected to be found in telco environments. Telefónica will utilize a state-of-art piloting environment called 5TONIC, an Open 5G Lab recognized as a Digital Innovation Hub (DIH) by the European Union. The site already has a deployed network infrastructure for supporting pre-5G trials and a number of use cases. The desired impact of this use case concerns the deployment of AI applications in Network virtualized infrastructure in an accountable and transparent way. The goal is to create accuracy of AI algorithms while preserving users' privacy.

Use case 2: Improving explainability, resilience and performance of cybersecurity analysis of 5G/4G/IoT networks

This use case focuses on cybersecurity risks, protection of 5G and IoT networks, analysis of encrypted traffic, and Root Cause Analysis. SPATIAL partner Montimage aims to render the techniques used or introduced more transparent, resilient to adversarial ML, precise (e.g., by combining several ML algorithms) and efficient (e.g., using distributed data and processing of ML techniques). The results of SPATIAL will be of great importance to improve these techniques, particularly concerning the use, resiliency, explainability and assessment of AI/ML. Techniques, guidelines and building blocks developed by the SPATIAL project will be considered and evaluated with respect to the improvements in the performance, transparency and precision they bring to the security analysis and algorithms. Use case 2 aims to create impact via better explainability, resiliency and distribution of AI/ML techniques. SPATIAL will allow improving the use and explainability of AI/ML techniques.

Use case 3: Accountable AI in Emergency eCall System

Fraunhofer FOKUS is in charge of use case 3 focusing on effective and accountable algorithms for analysing various data and automatically triggering an NG 112 call (i.e., eCall) in case of an emergency. The goal of this use case is to design and implement an explainable and accountable eCall functionality based on AI/ML algorithms within a Next Generation IP-based telecom platform with the capability of integrating rich-media emergency calls – a combination of voice, text, IoT sensors, social network information and video. AI/ML algorithms can be used within the available EMYNOS eCall demonstrator and must be made explainable and accountable for future product certification. In addition, the eCall demonstrator offers a high degree of complexity, so that the developed methods are robust and versatile, and easy transfer to other

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case studies can be achieved. This work is geared towards improving coordination and communication among citizens, call centers and first responders in emergency situations.

Use case 4: Resilient Cybersecurity Analytics

WithSecure aims to study evasion and poisoning attacks against and defenses for ML models used in cybersecurity. This use case deals with privacy, data handling costs and security risks. Its desired impact is the detection of advanced cyberattacks. The focus lies on implementing prototypes of dynamic attack detection systems (essentially data collection and analysis mechanisms) and experiment with attack tactics and techniques, to study their extent and key risks, and to validate and evaluate countermeasures proposed in SPATIAL.

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